

Exploring Motivations and Social Factors Influencing Disaster Relief Engagement: The first cross-sectional study in Syria.

Victoria Khnouf

Arab International University, Faculty of Business

Imad-Addin Almasri (✉ imad_almasri27@yahoo.com)

Damascus University, Faculty of Economics, Department of Applied Statistics <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4741-3721>

Raneem Ghazi Aldeki

AL-Sham Private University, Faculty of Administrative Sciences <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4370-971X>

Rania Zrair

AL-Sham Private University, Faculty of Administrative Sciences

Research Article

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Abstract

The current study explored and revealed in depth the motivations and social factors that drive engagement in disaster relief efforts. with 670 Participants, (Mean \pm SD = 34.9 \pm 13 years), mostly women (58.2%), (62.7%) have witnessed earthquake disaster in Syria, (73.1%) living in Damascus, (71.6%) with a university degree, (40.3%) is considered middle-classed. This research uncovers valuable insights into the relationships between demographics, disaster experiences, motivations, and engagement in disaster relief activities. The findings offer crucial perspectives on how individuals are influenced to contribute their efforts during times of crisis.

The Syrian society is found to be truly humane. Additionally, one of the most important findings was that there were significant relationships between some variables, such as gender and the motive of the environment in which the person grew up. Therefore, this study is considered to be the first cross-sectional research conducted in Syria and the largest one that sheds light on this phenomenon strongly with relevant evidence.

BACKGROUND:

The social dynamics surrounding engagement in disaster relief can vary significantly across diverse cultures. Different values, beliefs and practices shape the way people respond to natural disasters. Different cultures may prioritize individualism and self-reliance, while others emphasize collectivism and community support. However, these cultural differences are only one facet of the various dimensions that influence engagement in disaster relief. Socioeconomic status, educational background and access to resources play a significant role in determining the extent to which individuals engage in disaster relief.

METHODOLOGY:

This study includes a sample of 670 participants from the Syrian community who responded to a questionnaire that explores the motivations and social factors that influence engagement in disaster relief. The questionnaire was carefully designed and contains 30 questions. Data analysis was conducted using statistical techniques within (SPSS V.25). Descriptive statistics were used in the study to outline the demographic information of the sample, including frequencies, percentages, and mean \pm SD values. The chi-Square Independence Test was used to assess the relationships between qualitative variables such as gender, socioeconomic status, education level, and engagement in disaster relief activities.

RESULTS:

The results of the study offer valuable insights into the motivations and experiences of the participants in connection with their involvement in disaster relief. One particularly important finding was that 91% of participants attributed their engagement in disaster relief efforts to human motivation. While various motivations were explored, this emerged as the most influential, suggesting that deep-rooted human connection plays a significant role in motivating individuals to engage in disaster relief activities. and 62.7% of the sample witnessed earthquake disasters in Syria, and 61.2% actively engaged in volunteering during

the earthquakes. Furthermore, 46.3% believed that social media and traditional media influenced their social roles and motivation towards volunteering.

CONCLUSION:

This study provides essential insights into the motivations and social factors that influence engagement in disaster relief, particularly in the unique context of Syria. The study highlights the significance of understanding the connections between culture, personal experiences and motivations that influence individuals's engagement in disaster relief efforts. It also shows that human sensory motivation emerged as the most influential factor that drives volunteer engagement. These findings have significant implications for disaster relief organizations and policy makers ;thus, providing a foundation for developing more effective community engagement strategies in times of crisis.

Purpose:

The research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the dynamics of disaster response and provides information for organizations, policy makers and communities to develop targeted strategies. By recognizing cultural influences, gender dynamics and the power of emotional narratives, the study aims to improve community-driven disaster preparedness and response in Syria and globally. By conducting the first cross-sectional study of its kind in Syria, the research seeks to provide essential insights into the dynamics that drive individuals to get involved in times of crisis. The ultimate goal of this research is to provide valuable knowledge for disaster relief organizations, policy makers and communities, thereby facilitating the development of more effective strategies to engage individuals in times of crisis. Additionally, the study aims to improve understanding of the nuanced interplay between cultural influences, personal experiences and motivations, with a particular emphasis on the role of human sensory motivation in promoting volunteering. The findings of this study have the potential to guide the development of targeted disaster relief programs, volunteer initiatives, and media campaigns, promote a more resilient and community-driven approach to disaster management in Syria, and offer lessons that are applicable on a global scale.

Originality/value:

This study is considered an innovative investigation into the motivations and social factors that influence engagement in disaster relief, particularly in the Syrian context. As the first cross-sectional study conducted in Syria, it breaks new ground by uncovering complex relationships between demographic characteristics, disaster experiences and volunteer motivations. The emphasis on human sensory motivation and the influence of the media adds unique insights. This research contributes to the global understanding of disaster dynamics and offers a new perspective on the complex interplay of cultural influences, gender dynamics and emotional resonance. The findings provide actionable knowledge for disaster relief organizations and policy makers and pave the way for more effective, culturally sensitive strategies.

Introduction

Recognizing that cultural values and beliefs impact engagement underscores the importance of cultural sensitivity in disaster response and enables organizations to approach disaster response with greater respect and effectiveness. The findings also serve as a foundation for disaster relief organizations and policy makers by providing information for the development of policies and programs that are better aligned with the motivations and social factors that drive community responses during times of crisis [1].

Natural disasters and humanitarian crises have profound and far-reaching effects on communities and require rapid and effective responses from both local populations and international aid organizations. The resilience and strength of communities in such difficult times often depends on the willingness of individuals to participate in disaster relief [2]. Although disaster relief is a global imperative, the social dynamics and motivations underlying engagement can vary significantly across different cultural and geographic contexts [2].

One such unique and challenging context is Syria, a country struggling with a protracted conflict and multiple humanitarian crises. In Syria, as in many other parts of the world, individuals from diverse backgrounds are coming together to provide crucial support to people affected by disasters. However, the question of what motivates these individuals to participate in disaster relief and how social and cultural factors influence their participation remains complex and under-researched [1].

Our study marks a significant milestone as it is the first cross-sectional research endeavor of its kind to be conducted in Syria. Focusing on the motivations and social factors that drive individuals to participate in disaster relief efforts, this research attempts to unravel the intricate web of influences that shape community responses during times of crisis.

The Syrian context, characterized by rich cultural, social and economic diversity, provides a compelling backdrop to investigate these essential aspects of engagement in disaster relief [3]. The study encompasses a substantial and diverse sample of 670 participants to ensure a robust examination of the factors that influence engagement, while taking into account the nuanced variations within Syrian society. Through this research, we aim to gain valuable insights into the motivations, experiences and social factors underlying engagement in disaster relief in Syria. These findings will not only contribute to the body of knowledge on disaster management, but will also serve as a basis for disaster relief organizations, policy makers and the broader international community. Understanding the dynamics that drive individuals to step forward during disasters and the influences that shape their actions is critical to improving the effectiveness of disaster response efforts, both in Syria and beyond. [5] [6].

This research embarks on a journey to uncover the intricate threads that weave through the fabric of disaster relief engagement in Syria. It sheds light on the motivations that inspire individuals to act and the social factors that shape their contribution to their communities in times of great need [7][8].

Syrian society displays a mix of resilience, solidarity and challenges during crises and natural disasters. The impact of the protracted conflict and the complexity of the humanitarian situation highlight both the strengths and weaknesses of the social fabric. The response to these challenges involves a combination of local initiatives, international aid and efforts to rebuild and strengthen community ties [9][10][11].

In times of crisis, community support networks become crucial. Families, neighbors and local communities play a significant role in providing aid, including shelter, food and medical care. Informal networks and grassroots organizations often emerge to address the immediate needs of the affected population [12].

Materials And Methods

STUDY DESIGN:

An internet-based cross-sectional survey was designed using the Google Form platform. The survey questions were in Arabic and consisted mainly of multiple-choice and close-ended questions and a few open-ended questions; however, for some questions, participants were given the option to add other answers. The questions were reviewed by three experts for relevance and clarity. Thus, a draft of the survey was piloted on 20 participants to assess the comprehensibility and responsiveness of the questions. The validated survey was uploaded to professional and private groups on social media, namely Facebook and WhatsApp, and sent via email. Group members were asked to participate and forward the survey. It included a brief introduction on the purpose of the study, followed by general questions to gather demographic data from participants. The survey asked about personal experiences with natural disasters. Participation was voluntary, but an informed consent to participate in the study was required. (Supplement Q)

PARTICIPANTS:

Over a period of seven months, we carried out a social study with questionnaires among the Syrian population.

We went through several stages to prepare for the research, such as brainstorming sessions to create the questionnaire. Then, we tested the questionnaire with a small group of participants and adjusted it until it reached its final form. The data collection process took almost two months, from June 20 to August 30, 2023.

We recruited all participants through social media, which helped us to distribute our questionnaire to many Syrians. The questionnaire was accompanied by an informative introduction to the study, which emphasised the voluntary nature of the survey. A total of 670 individuals were enrolled. Although the questionnaire began as an opinion poll, the link to the survey was designed to in such a way to ensure that each respondent could only participate once to prevent repeated participations..

MEASUREMENT:

The questionnaire was divided into three parts. The first part collected socio-demographic information such as age, gender, place of residence and employment status of the respondents (whether they work for the

government, a private company, an NGO, a volunteer team, etc.). Respondents were also asked about their level of education. This data is shown in Table [1].

The second part of the questionnaire contained research questions on natural disasters in Syria. The results are shown in Table [3].

The third and final part of the questionnaire consisted of various questions on the personal opinions of the participants about the motivations that encourage people to volunteer in times natural disasters. The results are shown in Table [2] and Table [4].

DATA ANALYSES:

Statistical tests were used to analyze the research data, especially nominal and ordinal data, since most of the data were given as numbers and ratios. To avoid missing values in some questions, the valid percentage was utilized. To determine the correlation between social, economic and cultural factors and variables related to the interaction with natural disasters and the motives for it, the chi-square test (χ^2) was used to assess the relationships between different categorical variables and research questions. The Chi-square test is a statistical method that can be used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between two categorical variables. It helps researchers understand whether the observed frequencies of the categories differ significantly from the expected frequencies. Throughout the research, Chi-square tests were conducted for various sets of categorical variables such as gender, marital status, presence of children, work status, educational level and economic situation in relation to different research questions. The results of these tests are shown in [Tables 5, 6 and 7],

and the p-values were provided to indicate the level of significance. For instance, in Table [5], the Chi-Square test was used to examine the relationships between gender, marital status and participation in volunteering, contribution to media, and the influence of social and traditional media on motivation. The p-values associated with each test were indicated. If the p-value is below the significance level (which is usually set at 0.05), it suggests a statistically significant association between the variables. Similarly, chi-square tests were applied in [Tables 6 and 7] to examine relationships between the presence of children, working in the medical field, economic situation, educational level and various research questions. In conclusion, the Chi-Square tests in this research were instrumental in identifying statistically significant associations between various categorical variables providing valuable insight into how these demographic factors relate to individuals' experiences, motivations, and engagement in disaster relief.

A TRUF analysis was used for multiple-choice questions. In the research conducted , TURF (Total Unduplicated Reach and Frequency) analysis was used to assess and optimize the reach of the various motivations and factors influencing respondents

TURF analysis is a statistical technique commonly used in marketing and market research to determine the optimal combination of factors to maximize reach within a target audience.

The results of the TURF analysis Table [4] revealed that the most common motivations were human empathy (91.0%), a combination of human empathy and the place of residence during the disaster (95.5%), and a combination of human empathy, where the person lived, and the environment in which the person grew up (97.0%). These findings suggest that a multifaceted approach that takes these motivating factors into account would likely have the broadest appeal and engagement among the surveyed population. The TURF analysis provides valuable insights for decision makers by highlighting the combinations that offer the greatest overall reach while minimizing redundancy. In the context of this research, understanding the motivations that resonate most strongly with respondents can guide the development of targeted disaster relief programs, volunteer initiatives and media campaigns. This strategic approach helps focus efforts on the factors that have the greatest impact on active participation and engagement in disaster relief.

Statistical significance was determined as a $p < 0.05$ for all purposes.

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS-25) was used for all analyses.

SAMPLE SIZE:

The number of samples (n) was calculated using Cochran's formula, assuming a confidence level of 95.5% ($Z = 2$). The margin of error (e) was set at 5%, while the proportion (p) was estimated at 50% (or 0.5). The value of q was determined as (1-p).

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2} = \frac{(2)^2 * 0.5 * 0.5}{(0.05)^2} = 400$$

Therefore, based on a confidence level of 95.5% and a margin of error between 5%, our research required a sample size of 400 participants. We were able to collect 670 questionnaires, our original goal was to achieve a margin of error of 5%, which would have required us to collect more 400 questionnaires. However, we did it during the collection process, and after a full month of effort [13].

Results

General description of participants: These results provide a comprehensive overview of the demographic composition and experiences of participants in the study. The study included 670 participants ranging in age from 18 to 61 years, with a (mean \pm SD = 34.93 \pm 13.91 years). The gender distribution was 58.2% female and 41.8% male.

Of the participants who agreed to participate 100%, 41.8% were males and 58.2% were females, with 49.3 % stated that they were single, 51.8 % were married. The majority live in Damascus 73.1% and represent different economic situations. 71.6% are university students, 16.4% have a master's degree and 4.5% have a doctorate. Most attend public universities 76.1%. Employment status varies, with 23.9% working in the medical field. 56.7% are involved in volunteer work and 44.8% have children. Natural disaster exposure

includes: 62.7% have witnessed earthquakes, 3% forest fires and 34.3% both. Aleppo and Homs are the most frequently mentioned affected governorates. The majority were not in the affected governorates 86.6% were not in governorates affected by earthquakes. Table [1].

The motivations and social factors that influence involvement in disaster relief show a diverse range of responses among the participants. Self-proving motivation was affirmed by 26.9% of respondents, while 73.1% were uncertain. The influence of the environment in which the individual grew up was answered in the affirmative by 44.8% and in the negative by 55.2%. The place of residence in the case of disasters was also answered in the affirmative by 31.3% and in the negative by 68.7%. The status of work as a motivator had 25.4% agreement. Human Sensitivity Motivation showed strong positive endorsement, with 91% agreement. Recognition for work during disasters was agreed by 10.4%, while 56.7% agreed with media coverage. Social media and the influence of media on social roles and volunteer motivation received mixed responses with 46.3%, 43.3% and 29.9% respectively. These findings illustrate a nuanced landscape of motivations, indicating that factors such as personal validation, upbringing, and workplace status play distinctive roles in influencing participants' engagement in disaster relief. Table [2].

The findings in Table [3] indicate a significant level of volunteering during the earthquakes, varying perceptions of personal impact and a predominantly unharmed physical environment, highlighting the diverse experiences and responses of participants in the face of natural disasters in Syria. The majority, 61.2%, actively engaged in volunteer work during the earthquakes, while none reported involvement during the forest fires. Remarkably, 11.9% participated in both scenarios, while 26.9% did not contribute to volunteering. In terms of personal impact, 23.9% considered themselves affected by earthquakes, while the impact of wildfires was minimal 1.5%. A larger proportion, 67.2%, saw no personal impact from the natural disasters in Syria. Tragically, 97% suffered neither the loss of persons or houses nor physical harm. However, psychological damage was reported by 37.3% for earthquakes and 13.4% for both disaster scenarios.

The results of the TURF analysis (Total Unduplicated Reach and Frequency) on the motivations reveal the most frequent combinations. Human empathy proved to be the most prevalent motivation encompassing 91% of participants. The second most common combination included both human empathy and place of residence during the disaster, reaching a reach of 95.5%. The third and most extensive category included human sense (empathy), place of residence during the disaster and the environment in which the person grew up, with a reach of 97%. These results emphasise the multifaceted nature of motivations, with human sensitivity being a predominant and independent driver, while combinations of aspects of personal background and place of residence during the disaster further contribute to the complexity of motivations influencing participants' engagement in disaster relief, Table [4].

The participants' responses are listed below. Additionally, by comparing the P-value and the α -level (0.05), it is determined whether there is a correlation between the respondents' characteristics and their answer. If the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a correlation; if it is greater than 0.05, there is no correlation.

The relationship between gender, marital status and various research questions related to engagement and motivation for disaster relief. (fragment) The analysis reveals that there is a significant relationship between gender and volunteering in natural disasters, with a higher proportion of females 72.2% stating that they do not participate in such activities than the proportion of men 27.8%.

Additionally, a significant correlation is observed between marital status and volunteering during earthquakes. To illustrate, a larger percentage of married individuals 61.1% participated compared to single individuals 38.9%. However, there are no notable connections discovered between gender or marital status and their contribution to media coverage. Similarly, there are no significant associations found between gender or marital status and the perception of social media's impact on social roles and motivations, as well as motivations related to human sense, work status, place of residence during disasters, environment of upbringing, and self-proving motivations. These findings indicate that while gender and marital status may have an influence on specific aspects of disaster relief engagement, it does not necessarily extend to all dimensions examined in the study, as presented in Table [5].

The correlation between having children, involvement in volunteer work, employment in the medical sector, and various research inquiries pertaining to disaster relief is examined in this study. The analysis demonstrates that having children does not exhibit a significant connection with participating in voluntary activities during natural calamities, contributing to social media coverage, or perceiving the influence of social media on social roles and motivations. Similarly, there is no significant association between having children and motivations linked to human empathy, work status, location of residence during disasters, upbringing environment, and self-motivation for proving oneself. Furthermore, the outcomes indicate no significant relationships between engagement in volunteer work or working in the medical field. These findings imply that the presence of children and occupational factors may not strongly determine the level of engagement and motivations for disaster relief within the surveyed population in the Syrian context, as depicted in Table [6].

the results of the Chi-Square tests examining the relationship between the status of work, education level, economic situation, and research questions related to disaster relief engagement. The analysis reveals no significant associations between these demographic factors and participants' engagement in voluntary work during natural disasters, media contributions, perceived impact of social media on their social role and motivation toward volunteer work, motivations related to human sense, status of work, place of residence during disasters, environment in which the person grew up, and self-proving motivation. These findings suggest that, within the study's parameters, the status of work, education level, and economic situation do not significantly influence the disaster relief engagement and motivations of the surveyed individuals in the context of Syria, Table [7].

The research findings shed light on the intricate nature of motivations and social factors that influence the involvement of individuals in disaster relief efforts in Syria. While certain demographic variables exhibited significant correlations with specific motivations, others did not show any significant associations. These results offer valuable insights into comprehending the dynamics of community engagement during natural calamities within the Syrian context. The TURF analysis introduces a strategic element to the discourse by

identifying the motivations that occur most frequently. Human sensitivity, which encompasses both human perception and the location of residence during the disaster, along with a combination of human perception, place of residence, and the individual's upbringing environment, emerged as the motivations with the highest reach (97.0%). This analysis provides practical insights for decision-makers, suggesting that an approach that takes into account these multifaceted motivational factors would likely garner the widest appeal and engagement among the population surveyed.

It is evident that the results of the study suggest a positive and strong inclination among the Syrian people towards volunteer work and helping others. The significance level being less than 5 % (commonly interpreted as $p < 0.05$) typically implies statistical significance, indicating that the observed results are unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, the findings may lead to the conclusion that the motivation for social interaction and engagement in volunteer work among the 670 participants in the questionnaire is very high.

It is crucial to acknowledge that statistical significance does not necessarily imply the magnitude or practical importance of the impact. Nevertheless, the observation that the Syrian population exhibits a strong inclination towards social engagement and voluntary efforts is a favorable finding. This discovery holds significant implications for bolstering community resilience and support systems, especially in the face of natural disasters or crises.

Discussion

Our research provides a thorough exploration of the findings and their implications. It emphasizes the need for emotionally resonant narratives in relief campaigns, the influence of media in shaping motivations, and the importance of gender-sensitive and culturally informed approaches. Comprehensive research explores post-disaster dynamics with a focus on social support, emphasizing its role in forming resilient networks and its impact on the mental well-being of survivors [14]. Disasters elicit strong and quick physiological, emotional, and social reactions. Even in the most dramatic circumstances, survivors seldom become psychologically paralyzed. Instead, they burst into action, doing what they can to rescue and help others [14]. And examines disaster nursing competence, anticipatory stress, and motivation among nursing students in Taiwan, highlighting the need for innovative educational strategies [15].

The study's contribution extends beyond Syria, offering valuable lessons for disaster relief organizations and policymakers globally. By recognizing the complex interplay of factors influencing disaster relief engagement, Additionally, utilizing the community capital framework, by analyzing the influence of community characteristics on preparedness, response, and recovery, emphasizing the nuanced relationships between natural, political, social, and financial capitals in the context of different disasters [16]. By investigating various aspects of disaster preparedness in different cultural contexts the research explores the correlation between preparedness and cultural factors in Romania and Malta, highlighting specific cultural elements that can enhance readiness and effective communication [17]. But in our research contributes to the development of more effective, community-driven, and culturally sensitive strategies for disaster preparedness and response.

For example, impact of the Great East Japan Earthquake on social engagement and well-being is examined, revealing patterns of participation based on the extent of the disaster's impact [18]. Additionally, a preliminary investigation in Selangor, Malaysia, underscores the importance of addressing knowledge gaps to improve community preparedness [19]. The study also explores key aspects of disaster-related topics, encompassing community resilience drivers, effective communication during disasters using social media, and insights into evidence-based practices for disaster response [20]. So, our research provides a comprehensive analysis of the nuanced findings, their implications, and their broader relevance in the context of disaster relief engagement in Syria. Where The study's exploration of motivations and social factors offers a rich foundation for understanding the dynamics that drive individuals to actively participate in relief efforts during times of crisis. Also, the studies highlight factors influencing social resilience, the impact of a Facebook-based communication strategy on disaster response [21], and crucial considerations for policy development in the realm of disaster response, emphasizing stakeholder engagement, evidence-based approaches, research prioritization, and ethical considerations. Together, these studies provide valuable insights into enhancing community preparedness, communication strategies, and evidence-informed decision-making in the face of disasters [22]. In Taiwan highlights the need for improved disaster education among nursing students, emphasizing low competence levels but high motivation [23]. In Beijing underscores the importance of addressing social factors to enhance disaster response knowledge among residents, especially regarding human-made disasters, with implications for targeted education efforts [24]. This overview highlights recent global attention to public health crises and disaster preparedness, citing specific studies in South Korea on factors impacting the disaster competencies of healthcare professionals [25].

The identification of human sensory motivation as a predominant factor, influencing 91% of the participants, opens avenues for probing the emotional and psychological dimensions of volunteer engagement in disaster relief. The emphasis on human sensory motivation underscores the deeply ingrained connection individuals feel to the plight of others during disasters. This resonant connection speaks to the human capacity for empathy and compassion, suggesting that effective disaster relief campaigns should seek to evoke these emotional responses. Understanding the emotional underpinnings of volunteerism can inform the development of more impactful narratives and experiences in relief campaigns. By creating emotionally resonant stories and opportunities for involvement, organizations may stimulate higher rates of volunteerism and community participation. Additionally, a cross-sectional examination across eight countries underscores concerns about various risks, emphasizing the need for tailored disaster risk reduction strategies [26]. In the academic realm, a surge in interest in Academic Social Network Sites (ASNS) in China has led to research exploring factors influencing continuous usage intention, revealing contributors like satisfaction, perceived usefulness, and social identity [27].

Furthermore, the study's finding that 62.7% of the sample witnessed earthquake disasters in Syria emphasizes the prevalence of direct exposure to crises among the surveyed population. This direct exposure likely plays a pivotal role in shaping individuals' motivations to engage in disaster relief activities. It raises questions about the psychological impact of first-hand disaster experiences and how these experiences drive a sense of duty or responsibility to contribute to relief efforts. Exploring the psychological

mechanisms behind such motivations could deepen our understanding of the factors that mobilize individuals during times of crisis.

By shedding light on critical aspects in Guangdong Province, China, including the moderate disaster preparedness among emergency nurses and the factors influencing it [28]. Additionally, a systematic analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) disclosure in developing countries reveals the intertwined internal and external influences, motivations, and theoretical frameworks guiding such practices [29] [30]. The study's recognition of the influence of media, both social and traditional, on social roles and motivations toward volunteering adds another layer to the discussion. The acknowledgment by 46.3% of participants that media impacts their engagement suggests the power of communication channels in shaping public perceptions and responses to disasters. This finding invites reflection on the role of media in disaster risk reduction and preparedness campaigns. Organizations can leverage media channels to not only disseminate information but also to influence societal attitudes and motivations toward volunteering. This underscores the importance of strategic communication in the field of disaster relief.

Gender dynamics emerge as a notable aspect of the discussion, with the study revealing significant relationships between gender and motivations related to the environment in which individuals grew up. This raises important questions about the intersection of gender roles and cultural influences in disaster relief engagement. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing gender-sensitive approaches that ensure equitable participation. Additionally, the finding that more females did not participate in voluntary work during natural disasters highlights potential disparities that warrant further exploration. Addressing gender-specific barriers and motivations can contribute to more inclusive and effective disaster response strategies.

The focus on Syria as the study's context brings attention to the impact of cultural values and beliefs on disaster relief engagement. The findings emphasize the need for cultural sensitivity in relief efforts, urging organizations to approach disaster relief with a deep respect for the cultural context. This recognition of cultural influences provides an essential foundation for tailoring relief strategies to the specific needs and preferences of the local population. It also highlights the importance of involving communities in the design and implementation of relief programs to ensure cultural relevance and effectiveness.

Conclusion

This research sheds light on important insights into the factors that drive engagement in disaster relief efforts in the unique context of Syria. This significant study reveals several key findings that have far-reaching implications for disaster relief not only in Syria but also on a global scale.

Understanding the motivations and social factors that contribute to disaster relief engagement empowers communities to play a more active role in preparing for and responding to disasters. It can also foster stronger social cohesion within communities. When individuals come together to address disasters, it strengthens their bonds and creates a sense of shared purpose, which has broader positive implications for social unity. This self-reliance can result in more efficient and localized disaster relief efforts, ultimately enhancing community resilience. The identification of human sensory perception (Empathy) as the most

influential motivation can encourage organizations to create emotionally resonant narratives and experiences in their disaster relief campaigns. This, in turn, can stimulate higher rates of volunteerism and community participation. Moreover, Policymakers can utilize this research to inform the development of policies that promote and support engagement in disaster relief. By doing so, it can lead to more effective disaster management at both the local and national levels, ultimately resulting in more resilient communities that are better equipped to respond to disasters.

The crucial role of human sensory motivation in driving individuals to participate in disaster relief activities is underscored in this study, which emphasizes the significance of creating emotionally resonant narratives and experiences in relief campaigns. Furthermore, the study sheds light on the influence of gender in disaster relief engagement, highlighting the necessity for gender-sensitive approaches to ensure fair and equal participation. The recognition of the impact of cultural values and beliefs on engagement further emphasizes the importance of cultural sensitivity in relief efforts, enabling organizations to approach disaster relief with greater respect and effectiveness. These findings also serve as a fundamental resource for disaster relief organizations and policymakers, providing valuable insights for the development of policies and programs that are more attuned to the motivations and social factors that drive community responses during times of crisis.

The comprehensive analysis of the research data reveals valuable insights into the factors that affect the involvement of the surveyed population in Syria in disaster relief efforts. The findings indicate a complex relationship between gender, marital status, and various dimensions of disaster-related activities. While there is a significant correlation between gender and voluntary work during natural disasters, with a higher percentage of females not participating, this pattern does not uniformly extend to other aspects such as media coverage, perception of social media impact, and specific motivational factors. Marital status demonstrates significance in terms of contributing to voluntary work during earthquakes but does not consistently show associations in other domains. The study highlights the intricate nature of motivations and responses to natural disasters, suggesting that gender and marital status may influence specific aspects of disaster relief engagement. This underscores the need for a more targeted and nuanced approach in disaster management strategies. Further research and exploration are necessary to deepen our understanding of the complex interplay between demographic factors and humanitarian efforts in the face of natural disasters.

LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

Research limitations/implications:

Social implications:

This research has significant social implications. Exploring the motivations and social factors that drive involvement in disaster relief has the potential to strengthen community resilience and promote greater social cohesion, ultimately leading to a more unified and resilient society. The findings of the study

underscore the importance of gender equality, urging organizations to adopt gender-sensitive approaches to disaster relief. Recognizing the influence of culture can also result in relief efforts that are more culturally sensitive. Additionally, the study highlights the impact of emotionally resonant narratives in inspiring volunteerism and active community participation. It raises public awareness about the complexities of engaging in disaster relief, empowering communities and informing the development of policies. Ultimately, this research contributes to a more effective disaster relief landscape driven by communities in Syria and offers valuable insights that can be applied to disaster management worldwide.

Practical implications:

This research serves as a steppingstone for further in-depth investigations into disaster relief engagement in Syria. Its findings have wide-ranging relevance to disaster relief endeavors globally, thus rendering it a valuable asset for international organizations and researchers aiming to improve the efficiency of their relief initiatives.

limitations:

The study faced several challenges and limitations during the data collection process. The reliance on a single method of data collection, namely surveys, may restrict the depth of insights when compared to a mixed-methods approach that incorporates qualitative data. However, due to the prevailing circumstances in Syria following the crisis, it is not feasible to adopt such an approach. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design employed in the study only provides a snapshot of data at a specific point in time. Consequently, it does not allow for the examination of changes in motivations and social factors over an extended period..

Acknowledging these limitations is importance in upholding the integrity of the research and informing future studies in the field of disaster relief engagement. Moreover, addressing these limitations in future research endeavors can contribute to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the intricate complexities involved in motivating and engaging individuals in disaster relief activities.

Declarations

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS:

The datasets collected and analyzed during the current study are available. Some restrictions apply to the availability of these data but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE:

Ethical approval was not required for this study as it did not involve any interventional procedures. However, all participants willingly granted their consent in the questionnaire, which served as the means of data collection. Additionally, the study was carried out under the supervision of Two esteemed universities in Syria, namely Arab International University's Faculty of Business Administration and AL-Sham Private

University's Faculty of Administrative Sciences. This was done to ensure that high ethical and scientific standards were met during the study.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION:

As a part of the questionnaire, the participants were asked for their informed consent.

COMPETING INTERESTS:

The authors state that they have no conflicts of interest, whether financial or non-financial.

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Not applicable.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION:

Victoria Khnouf & Imad-Addin Almasri :Conceptualization, Methodology, designed and applied the questionnaire, drafting, editing, reviewing contributing to Result.

Victoria Khnouf: Literature Review, Conclusion, Discussion, translating and supervisor.

Rania Zrair: Conclusion, Discussion, contributing to editing and reviewing and supervisor.

Raneem Ghazi Aldeki: Literature Review, Conclusion, Discussion, translating, editing, and reviewing

Imad-Addin Almasri: Statistical Analyzed and interpreted the Data.

Tables legends and Supplement:

Table 1: Description of Demographic and General Questions.

Table 2: Description affected of Syria's natural disasters.

Table 3: Motivations of the Social Factors Influencing Disaster Relief Engagement.

Table 4: TURF Analysis for frequent motivations.

Table 5: Relationship between Gender, social status, and Research Questions.

Table 6: Relationship between having children, Volunteering, Medical Work and Research Questions.

Table 7: Relationship between Status of work, Education Level, economic status, and Research Questions.

Supplement A: Supplementary Tables.

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Tables

Table (1) Description of Demographic and General Questions

I Agree to Participate in the Research	YES	670 (100%)	
Gender	Male	280 (41.8%)	
	Female	390 (58.2%)	
Social status	Single	330 (49.3%)	
	Married	340 (51.8%)	
Place of Residence	Damascus	490 (73.1%)	
	Damascus Countryside	180 (26.9%)	
Economic status	Weak (less than 500 thousand)	300 (44.8%)	
	Intermediate (500 to 1 million)	270 (40.3%)	
	Good (1 million to 2 million)	60 (9%)	
	Excellent (over 2 million)	40 (6%)	
Education Level	Secondary or less	50 (7.5%)	
	undergraduate	480 (71.6%)	
	master	110 (16.4%)	
	PhD	30 (4.5%)	
Educational Institution	don't study at university	50 (7.5%)	
	private university	110 (16.4%)	
	public university	510 (76.1%)	
	don't work	140 (20.9%)	
Status of Work	work part-time	120 (17.9%)	
	Work full-time	280 (41.8)	
	private business	130 (19.4%)	
	don't work	140 (20.9%)	
Employer Institution	government sector	150 (22.4%)	
	private company	240 (35.8%)	
	Assembly	900 (13.4%)	
	organization	100 (1.5%)	
	own business	300 (4.5%)	
	Do you Work in the Medical Field	YES	160 (23.9%)
	Do you have Volunteer Work	YES	380 (56.7%)
Do you have Children	YES	300 (44.8%)	
Age	Mean \pm SD	34.9 \pm 13	
	Max	61	
	Min	18	
	Range	43	
Have you experienced a natural disaster in Syria?	Just earthquake	420 (62.7%)	
	Judt forest fires	20 (3%)	
	Earthquake and forest fires	230 (34.3%)	
Were you in one of the governorates affected by earthquakes	NO	580 (86.6%)	
	Aleppo	40 (6%)	
	Hama	30 (4.5%)	
	Lattakia	10 (1.5%)	
	Tartous	10 (1.5%)	
Were you in one of the governorates affected by the forest fires	NO	550 (82.1%)	
	Homs	50 (7.5%)	
	Hama	10 (1.5%)	
	Lattakia	20 (3%)	
	Tartous	40 (6%)	

Table (2) Description affected of Syria's natural disasters

	Earthquake	Forest fires	Both	NO
Have you contributed during a natural disaster to any voluntary work	410 (61.2%)	0 (0.00%)	80 (11.9%)	180 (26.9%)
Do you consider yourself affected by one of Syria's natural disasters?	160 (23.9%)	10 (1.5%)	50 (7.5%)	450 (67.2%)
Affected by loss of one or more persons	20 (3%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	650 (97%)
Damaged by loss of house	20 (3%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	650 (97%)
Damaged by loss of work source	30 (4.5%)	10 (1.5%)	0 (0.00%)	360 (94%)
Psychologically damaged	250 (37.3%)	20 (3%)	9 (13.4%)	310 (46.3%)
Physically harmed	20 (3%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	650 (97%)

Table (3) Motivation of the **Social** Factors Influencing Disaster Relief Engagement

	YES	NO	Maybe
Self-proving Motivation	18 (26.9%)	49 (73.1%)	NA
The environment in which the person grew up	30 (44.8%)	37 (55.2%)	NA
The person's locations during the disaster	21 (31.3%)	460 (68.7%)	NA
The nature of the person's work	170 (25.4%)	500 (74.6%)	NA
Human Sense Motivation	610 (91%)	60 (9%)	NA
Have you received any appreciation for your voluntary work	70 (10.4%)	600 (89.6%)	NA
Have you contributed media posts about disasters on social media?	380 (56.7%)	290 (43.3%)	NA
Do you think the media influenced your social role and your motivation towards work	310 (46.3%)	160 (23.9%)	200 (29.9%)

Table (4) TURF Analysis for frequent motivations

	group size	N %
human sensitivity	1	610 (91.0%)
Human sense, person's location	2	640 (95.5%)
Human sense, person's location, the environment in which the person grew up	3	650 (97.0%)

Table (5) Relationship between Gender, social status and Research Questions.

		Gender		Sig*	Social Status		Sig*
		Female	Male		Married	Single	
Have you contributed during a natural disaster to any voluntary work	No	130 (72.2%)	50 (27.8%)	0.05>0.364	110 (61.1%)	70 (38.9%)	0.05>0.169
	earthquake	220 (53.7%)	190 (46.35)		160 (39.0%)	250 (61.0%)	
	both	40 (50.0%)	40 (50.0%)		30 (37.5%)	50 (62.5%)	
Have you contributed media posts about disasters on social media?	No	150 (51.7%)	140 (48.3%)	0.05>0.347	110 (37.9%)	180 (62.0%)	0.05>0.367
	Yes	240 (63.2%)	140 (36.8%)		190 (50.0%)	190 (50.0%)	
The media influenced your social role and your motivation towards work	No	60 (37.5%)	100 (62.5%)	0.05>0.157	90 (56.3%)	70 (43.7%)	0.05>0.553
	Yes	200 (64.5%)	110 (35.5%)		110 (35.5%)	200 (64.5%)	
	maybe	130 (65.0%)	70 (35.0%)		100 (50.0%)	100 (50.0%)	
The motivation of Human Sense	No	40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	0.05>1.660	30 (50.0%)	30 (50.0%)	0.05>0.874
	Yes	350 (57.4%)	260 (42.6%)		270 (44.2%)	340 (55.8%)	
Motivation of the nature of the person's work	No	320 (64.0%)	180 (36.0%)	0.05>0.099	230 (46.0%)	270 (54.0%)	0.05>0.448
	Yes	70 (41.2%)	100 (58.8%)		70 (41.2%)	100 (58.8%)	
Motivation the person's locations during the disaster	No	300 (65.2%)	160 (34.8%)	0.05>0.085	180 (39.1%)	280 (60.9%)	0.05>0.194
	Yes	90 (42.9%)	120 (57.1%)		120 (57.1%)	90 (42.9%)	
Motivation of the environment in which the person grew up	No	260 (70.3%)	110 (29.7%)	0.05>0.026	200 (52.4%)	180 (48.6%)	0.05>0.659
	Yes	130 (43.3%)	170 (56.7%)		110 (36.6%)	190 (64.4%)	
Self-proving motive	No	300 (61.2%)	190 (38.8%)	0.05>0.409	220 (44.9%)	270 (55.1%)	0.05>0.485
	Yes	90 (50.0%)	90 (50.0%)		80 (44.4%)	100 (55.6%)	

***Pearson Chi-Square Test**

Table (6) Relationship between having children, Volunteering, Medical Work and Research Questions.

		have children?		have volunteer work?		work in the Medical Field?	
		YES	Sig*	YES	Sig*	YES	Sig*
Have you contributed during a natural disaster to any voluntary work	No	110 (61.1%)	0.05>0.184	80 (44.4%)	0.05>0.325	40 (22.2%)	0.05>0.981
	earthquake	170 (41.5%)		240 (58.5%)		100 (24.4%)	
	both	20 (25.0%)		60 (75.0%)		20 (25.0%)	
Have you contributed media posts about disasters on social media?	No	120 (41.4%)	0.05>0.625	170 (58.6%)	0.05>0.783	70 (24.1%)	0.05>0.966
	Yes	180 (47.4%)		210 (55.3%)		90 (23.7%)	
The media influenced your social role and your motivation towards work	No	90 (56.3%)	0.05>0.518	90 (56.3%)	0.05>0.729	40 (25.0%)	0.05>0.514
	Yes	120 (38.7%)		190 (61.3%)		90 (29.0%)	
	maybe	90 (45.0%)		100 (50.0%)		30 (15.0%)	
The motivation of Human Sense	No	30 (50.0%)	0.05>0.787	20 (33.3%)	0.05>0.226	20 (33.3%)	0.05>0.569
	Yes	270 (44.3%)		360 (59.0%)		140 (23.0%)	
Motivation of the nature of the person's work	No	240 (48.0%)	0.05>0.363	240 (48.0%)	0.05>0.014	100 (20.0%)	0.05>0.201
	Yes	60 (35.3%)		140 (82.4%)		60 (35.3%)	
Motivation the person's locations during the disaster	No	200 (43.5%)	0.05>0.752	230 (50.0%)	0.05>0.101	80 (17.4%)	0.05>0.065
	Yes	100 (47.6%)		150 (71.4%)		80 (38.1%)	
Motivation of the environment in which the person grew up	No	190 (51.4%)	0.05>0.229	170 (45.9%)	0.05>0.048	80 (21.6%)	0.05>0.630
	Yes	110 (36.7%)		210 (70.0%)		80 (26.7%)	
Self-proving motive	No	230 (46.9%)	0.05>0.557	250 (51.0%)	0.05>0.121	110 (22.4%)	0.05>0.650
	Yes	70 (38.9%)		130 (72.2%)		50 (27.8%)	

***Pearson Chi-Square Test**

Table (7) Relationship between Status of work, Education Level, economic status and Research Questions.

		economic status	Education Level	Status of work
		Sig*	Sig*	Sig*
Have you contributed during a natural disaster to any voluntary work	No	0.05>0.533	0.05>0.524	0.05>0.861
	earthquake both			
Have you contributed media posts about disasters on social media?	No	0.05>0.318	0.05>0.269	0.05>0.853
	Yes			
The media influenced your social role and your motivation towards work	No	0.05>0.091	0.05>0.664	0.05>0.566
	Yes			
The motivation of Human Sense	No	0.05>0.484	0.05>0.822	0.05>0.497
	Yes			
Motivation of the nature of the person's work	No	0.05>0.546	0.05>0.219	0.05>0.063
	Yes			
Motivation the person's locations during the disaster	No	0.05>0.570	0.05>0.390	0.05>0.002
	Yes			
Motivation of the environment in which the person grew up	No	0.05>0.345	0.05>0.871	0.05>0.241
	Yes			
Self-proving motive	No	0.05>0.134	0.05>0.856	0.05>0.660
	Yes			

***Pearson Chi-Square Test**

Supplementary Files

This is a list of supplementary files associated with this preprint. Click to download.

- [FinalQuestionnaire.docx](#)
- [FinalSupplementaryTable.docx](#)